

Socket Evaluation Questionnaire

This questionnaire was designed to assess the quality of fit and level of comfort experienced while wearing a transtibial prosthetic socket. Please carefully read and answer all questions. Some questions can be answered by placing a vertical stripe across a horizontal bar. Place a single stripe at a desired level for each of these questions. Your answer can be all the way to the right as in this example, which means your reply to this question is "excellent":

Or your answer can be all the way to the left as in this example, which means your reply to this question is "terrible":

Or your answer can be anywhere in between as you see fit to provide an intermediate answer, e.g.:

You may also be asked to draw a region on your limb. You can draw by circling a region as shown here, for a region labelled 1 by the user:

Please do not hesitate to ask one of the researchers if you have any questions.

1. Rate how happy you are with this prosthetic socket

EXTREMELY UNHAPPY

EXTREMELY HAPPY

2. Rate the fit of this prosthetic socket

TERRIBLE

EXCELLENT

3. Rate the weight of this prosthetic socket

TERRIBLE

EXCELLENT

4. Rate how often you felt off balance when wearing this socket

ALL THE TIME

NOT AT ALL

5. Rate the feel (such as temperature and texture) of this prosthetic socket (including sock and liner) on your residual limb

WORST POSSIBLE

BEST POSSIBLE

6. Rate the ease of putting on this prosthetic socket

TERRIBLE

EXCELLENT

7. Rate how this prosthetic socket looks

TERRIBLE EXCELLENT

8. Rate how often this prosthetic socket makes squeaking, clicking or belching sounds

ALWAYS NEVER

9. If it made any sounds, rate how bothersome these sounds are to you

EXTREMELY BOTHERSOME NOT AT ALL

10. Rate how much you sweat inside this prosthetic socket

EXTREME AMOUNT NOT AT ALL

11. Rate your overall comfort while sitting

TERRIBLE EXCELLENT

12. Rate your overall comfort while standing

TERRIBLE EXCELLENT

Subject ID: _____

Date: _____

13. Rate your overall comfort while walking

TERRIBLE

EXCELLENT

14. If you have any pain, how intense is it?

EXTREMELY INTENSE

EXTREMELY MILD

15. If you have any pain, how bothersome is it?

EXTREMELY BOTHERSOME

NOT AT ALL

16. Rate your comfort at your PATELLA TENDON while standing still

17. Rate your comfort at your OUTER SIDE while standing still

18. Rate your comfort at your MID-TIBIA while standing still

19. Rate your comfort at your LOWER-TIBIA while standing still

20. Rate your comfort at your INNER-SIDE while standing still

21. Rate your comfort at your UPPER CALF while standing still

22. Rate your comfort at your LOWER CALF while standing still

23. Are there any other regions region on your limb that are painful? Describe up to three additional regions and draw using dots on the figure provided.

Region number

Region description

1.

2.

3.

Draw and label any additional regions

Rate your comfort at region 1:

TERRIBLE

EXCELLENT

Rate your comfort at region 2:

TERRIBLE

EXCELLENT

Rate your comfort at region 3:

TERRIBLE

EXCELLENT

Subject ID: _____
Date: _____

24. Please provide any additional comments below:

Lined area for providing additional comments.